

A perspective on 50% solar power evolution to support 100% CO₂ free electrical energy production

Mihai Sanduleac
University Politehnica of Bucharest
Department of Electrical Power Engineering
Bucharest, Romania
mihai.sanduleac@gmail.com

Abstract— The 100% CO₂ free electrical energy production is a new international goal for mitigating climate change. In this race towards achieving this goal till year 2050, solar photovoltaic production is one of the important variable of the equation. But is it feasible in terms of scaling up in this short period the today world production of photovoltaic equipment? How far we are with today achievements and what effort is needed worldwide to accomplish this challenge? The paper presents a possible evolution of solar equipment manufacturing and gives an image of the effort needed to accomplish the goal in different scenarios of having 50% PV production in a mix of energy production targeting 100% CO₂ free electrical energy production until 2035, 2040, 2045 or 2050. It is considered that the remaining 50% will be covered by other CO₂ free technologies, such as wind, hydro and nuclear energy production. The scenario results endorse that the Paris Agreement targets are feasible in terms of panel production capacity and that there are options for earlier deployments, specifically applicable until 2040 or 2045, with lower CO₂ emissions till 2050, to better address climate concerns.

Keywords—PV production, 100% CO₂ free energy, 50% PV

I. INTRODUCTION

The aim for achieving the goal of 100% CO₂ free electrical energy production has at least three main reasons:

a) the global warming threat, as main driver for reducing as soon as possible greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions; this situation is widely accepted by international bodies [1] and ask for clear actions for reducing global warming as soon as possible;

b) the need to stop the pollution caused by burning CO₂ associated fuels; pollution is considered a greater global threat than Ebola and HIV, according to warnings by the World Health Organisation [2]; there are countries and cities where the pollution became a high concern and the awareness of this situation is increasingly shown officially [3];

c) as climate is changing no matter the reason, local resilience becomes more important than ever; situations such as Puerto Rico power system heavily affected by the Maria storm in 2017 is the latest proof of nature power in destroying transport and distribution of electrical energy [4], bringing new threats not seriously considered before and asking for distributed generation, with PV production as main candidate to improve local resilience in case of extreme weather.

Any of those reasons is enough to pursue for clean energy solutions, and this is even more necessary as all three aspects are solid.

There are mainly two levels of pursuing the goal of decreasing / stopping CO₂ emissions:

a) one which considers renewable generation combined with nuclear electricity production, both being CO₂ free;

b) one which ask for electrical energy production based only on renewables, which is supported by those which became very much concerned of possible damages of nuclear power plants. This approach is gaining support especially after Fukushima nuclear disaster.

There are also other options, such as still using fossil fuels with carbon capture technology, but this option is still considered to be expensive, while new advancements in renewables technologies are proving that they become more and more economic and that they compete any traditional energy production, especially in countries with high solar irradiance [5]. Carbon capture by planting a huge number of trees is part of the solution, especially for sequestration of excess CO₂ after the carbon neutrality has been reached.

Traditional renewable electricity production has been obtained with big hydro-plants, many of them having also the advantage of lakes acting as big storage means, in order to transform potential energy of the water in the reservoirs at the moments needed in the power systems. Even if hydro-plants are excellent sources of CO₂ free electrical energy, most of the good places have been already used; new hydro-plants may be in many cases more expensive and the environmental change to allow the construction of the lakes behind the dams can be an issue as well.

The today main champions of the new wave of renewables remain wind and solar based electricity production, even if other means need to be considered as well, such as using biomass, waves energy or other solutions.

Renewables based on wind are very promising and have a high potential globally, but the production facilities need to be placed in proper regions where the average wind speed gives attractiveness for the investment. For this reason, energy production based on wind cannot be obtained everywhere and the energy transportation to main consumption areas can be a challenge. Solar energy production has a greater potential to be distributed over the Earth, at any latitude with acceptable solar

radiance. The today German PV investment show that even at latitudes of 50 or even 55 degrees it is still feasible to get electrical energy from PV plants. In countries with high solar irradiance the PV production becomes even more attractive.

But high penetration of PV plants need also adequate and timely PV panels industry to support the huge installations expected in the next period. However, the production capacity of PV panels and its roadmap for developing the corresponding factory capacity worldwide has been only indirectly addressed. For instance, in [6] it is forecasted that PV (installed) capacity could reach 1,760 GW in 2030, accounting for as much as 7% of global power generation. This target would require an average annual growth PV panels production capacity of 15% ($(1.148)^{13} = 6 = \text{approx. } 1760 \text{ GWp installed PV in } 2030$ compared with 295 GWp in 2017 [7]). The production capacity of PV panels need to be deducted, and the increase of 15% per year would mean from 2017 production of PV panels of around 100 GWp [7] to reach in 2030 around $100 \times (1.15)^{13} = 615 \text{ GW PV panel production}$.

In [8] is considered a technology roadmap for solar PV energy – envisioning PV's share of global electricity rising up to 16% by 2050. However, in the study the global energy-related CO₂ emissions target in 2050 is considered as being only 50% below current level, input data which ask for a revision if we target to limit global temperature rise by 2050 to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels.

In [9], the study shows also that an electricity system with 100% renewables is possible to be attended in 2050 and the PV share is considered to be 69% of total electricity production. The study considers only one scenario of PV deployment and does not address directly the PV panels production in order to assess the dimension and feasibility of the proposed roadmap. The study [10] implements the roadmaps for 2050 to avoid 1.5°C global warming and shows the feasibility for 139 countries to be powered only by wind, water and sunlight.

Even if different documents address future PV energy production in different ways, there is no clear assessment made about the scenarios on PV panels production capacity to be supported by the PV industry, in order to meet low or no GHG emissions in 2050, an essential milestone year in the context of Paris Agreement on Climate Change [11].

The paper considers a demanding worldwide scenario towards CO₂ free energy production, where half of the energy is obtained from PV facilities, as a more balanced approach compared with [9]. The rest of needed electrical energy is considered to be obtained with wind, hydro and nuclear, in a proportion which is not here analyzed. Even if solar production may be less than 50% of the total energy need (e.g. 1/3 PV, 1/3 wind and 1/3 hydro and nuclear), this paper intends to assess this 50% PV share challenging situation for a more “solar based” portfolio. If this PV share shows to be feasible, more balanced mix of renewables production may be feasible as well.

II. TODAY PV PRODUCTION AND WORLD CONTEXT

The renewable energy installations grown in 2016 with 131 TWh in wind (15.6%) and with 77 TWh in solar (29.6%) [12],

overpassing in total 3.2% of electrical energy produced worldwide.

The total production of PV panels was around 70 GWp in 2016 and reached around 100 GWp in 2017, while around half of it is used in China alone [13].

World electrical energy production was 24800 TWh in 2016 [12], which correspond to a worldwide average electrical power over the year of 2830 GW.

If 50% of this power need to be obtained from PVs, by considering an average capacity factor over all world PV installments of approx. 13% (corresponding to 1140 hours per year), it can be assessed in a simplified manner the worldwide effort needed for reaching this target.

Today we have an installed PV power of 295.9 GW (2017), which is an increase from the previous 2016 year, when we had installed 224.7 GW [7].

The paper analyses possible scenarios for the remaining 33 years till 2050, while trying to suggest accomplished targets in shorter time frames inside the 2035-2050 period.

III. ASPECTS RELATED TO STORAGE NEEDS

In the model applied for simulating PV production it has been considered only the electrical energy produced and the capacity factor of the installed power. As in renewables production there is also the problem of having energy in other periods than when it is needed (being produced during the daytime but mostly consumed during the evening), storage is a need in order to mitigate the situation.

Although storage is very important for being able to equalize the production and consumption, this paper is focusing on the PV fabrication needs, thus the storage issue is considered to be assessed separately, in future works. However, it is highly probably that the storage needs for electrical vehicles will overpass the need in power systems, thus being not a shortage problem for the grid, but an issue to be solved anyhow in the automotive industry, in order to advance towards fully electrified transportation.

IV. SCENARIOS FOR THE FUTURE

We are considering the following assumptions:

- The average world production need to increase each year with a factor K_{GROW} in order to cover the grow in consumption; in our tests, K_{GROW} has been chosen to be equal to 1%, which means that from the production of year 2016 of 24800 TWh it will be reached in 2050 a production of 34784 TWh, which means a grow of around 40% during a 24 years timespan. This situation can be consistent with various factors which have opposite effects on global energy consumption: the grow of energy consumption in emerging countries and with vehicle consumption shift to electrical energy – as increasing factors, and with higher efficiency in using the energy and car sharing deployments – as decreasing factor. The evolution of the total world power production is presented in Figure 1, as linear function pointing a scenario with combined influences, as

described before. Complementary scenarios asking for “More energy” or being “More efficient” are also depicted, however the paper is focusing on the “combined influences” scenario as basis for the assessment.

Figure 1 – Average power produced in the world – the scenario of the study

- The increase in PV efficiency is considered to be 2% per year, which allows that today average efficiency of 15% (based on today 16%-17% efficiency combined with lower efficiencies for earlier PVs already installed) to grow to 28% in 2050, which is still a reserved assumption, because emerging technologies such as perovskite, quantum dots and graphene may bring much higher efficiencies even sooner than in 2030.

- The production of PV panels need to cover also the change of PV modules which have already passed their period of life. If this period is considered to be 25 years, 4% of older PV panels need to be refurbished, but as the PV installment is growing in time, around half of this percentage may correspond to existing production of PV panels, so it has been considered a value of only 2% from current park of PV instalments; the factor is marked as $K_{REPLACEMENT}$; moreover, for simplification, the lifetime remains 25 years even in 2050, although we may expect higher life expectancy based on technological advancements.

The following main formulas apply:

$$P_{PROD_PV}(year_k) = P_{PROD_PV}(year_{k-1}) * (1 + K_{INC_PV} + K_{REPLACEMENT}) \quad (1)$$

$$E_{WORLD}(year_k) = E_{WORLD}(year_{k-1}) * (1 + K_{GROW}) \quad (2)$$

$$P_{CAPACITY_PV}(year_k) = P_{CAPACITY_PV}(year_{k-1}) + P_{PROD_PV}(year_{k-1}) \quad (3)$$

$$E_{PV}(year_k) = P_{CAPACITY_PV}(year_k) * ToU(year_k) \quad (4)$$

$$ToU(year_k) = ToU(year_{k-1}) * (1 + Ef_{GROW}) \quad (5)$$

where:

$P_{PROD_PV}(year k)$ is the production capacity in a year

K_{INC_PV} is the increase (growth) factor from year k-1 to year k.

ToU is the equivalent number of hours of a PV producing at nominal power; the value in 2017 is taken 1175h and is increasing 2% each year, due to the yearly efficiency growth $Ef_{GROW} = 2\%$ in our simulations

$P_{CAPACITY_PV}(year k)$ is the total PV installed capacity up to the year k .

To be noted that in the last part of the PV panels factory capacity evolution the factor K_{INC_PV} will have negative values, meaning that the PV production capacity decreases when approaching the target. After approaching the target of 50% energy production with PV, it is considered that the production will cover only refurbishments and maintenance.

In order to make a comprehensive analysis, four scenarios have been considered for the world total PV production capacity. Scenarios have been chosen such that they cover a palette of possible targets for complete PV production achievement starting from 2050 down to earlier time horizons, 2045, 240 and 2035 respectively:

- Scenario 0: a *slow* ramp of PV production growth, which brings a 50% world electricity production from PV panels in the year 2050. Number zero denoted basic deployment, meaning entire share of PV production is reached only at the limit of the period, thus being labeled as “low”.
- Scenario 1: a *moderate-slow* ramp of PV production growth, which brings a 50% world electricity production from PV panels in the year 2045, meaning 5 years before 2050; the reason for more ambitious targets is that earlier achievements correspond to less CO₂ emissions, which can contribute to improved climate change actions.
- Scenario 2: a *moderate-high* ramp of PV production growth, which brings a 50% world electricity production from PV panels around the year 2040, meaning 10 years before 2050. Scenario 2 and 1 are labeled as two levels of “moderate”.
- Scenario 3: an *aggressive* ramp of PV production growth, which brings a 50% world electricity production from PV panels around the year 2035, meaning 15 years before 2050.

The scenarios aim to target possible political endorsements, from 100% renewables or 100% CO₂ free policies in 2050 to more ambitious targets down to 2035 [14].

Figure 2 shows the results of the PV panels production simulation in each of the four scenarios.

Figure 2 – Evolution of the PV panels production capacity for four scenarios.

It can be observed that the most aggressive scenario, reaching the complete target of 50% renewables with PV in 2035 is asking for a maximum PV panel production capacity of around 600 GWp, which is 6 times more than 2017 worldwide capacity. However, the other three scenarios, obtaining 50% renewables with PV in 2040, 2045 and 2050 ask for only approximate 400 GWp in PV panels production capacity, which is 33% less in terms of PV factories investments compared with scenario 3, thus more feasible. All scenarios, except scenario 3, reduce their capacity of PV panels production after reaching the 50% PV production target to around 100 GWp, which correspond to the need for repairing and for refurbishments of existing PV plants, which has been considered as being 2% of installed capacity at the current year (the factor $K_{REPLACEMENT}$ used in (1)).

Figure 3 shows the evolution of the PV production share in the energy mix, from the today small amount up to the target of 50% share, in each of the four scenarios. The figure is consistent with the assumptions of the scenarios reaching the maximum share in 2035, 2040, 2045 and 2050.

Figure 3 – Evolution of the PV based electricity production share [%] for the four scenarios.

Figure 4 shows the evolution of the PV panels capacity production growth in each of the four scenarios.

Figure 4 – Evolution of the PV production capacity growth for the four scenarios.

The 34% growth expected for year 2017 is taken as highest growth factor (K_{INC_PV}) in the entire studied period. One can see that scenario 1 has also slower growth factors than the scenarios 2 and 3.

Near the four target years (2035, 2040, 2045 and 2050) the growth becomes negative, because after reaching the target there is a need for PV panels only for replacement (total share of 50% PV production has been reached) and for the small increase in consumption due to the factor K_{GROW} . For scenario zero the negative growth is expected after 2050, resulting in an excess of PV production after 2050 which may be eventually needed for other electrified energy segments of the global economy.

By analyzing the evolution of PV panels production and evolution in each situation (Fig. 2 and 4), one can make several comments:

- The moderate-low scenario 1 for reaching 50% PV electricity production in the energy mix ask for similar peak production capacity as for slow scenario, meaning around 380 GWp panels produced per year. This is around 3.8 the today PV panels yearly production;
- The moderate-high ramp of production for attending the 50% PV mix target in 2040 ask for a peak world production capacity of around 420 GWhp/year; this scenario is not much different in PV panels factory investment from the previous scenarios zero and 1, thus showing that it can be attractive as well, while CO2 emissions can be diminished, to be treated in next section;
- The shortest term (aggressive) of reaching 50% production with PV panels in 2035 ask for a peak production capacity of 600 GWp /year, which is nearly 6 times the today worldwide capacity of PV panels production and around 50% higher than in the other three scenarios.

Figure 5 presents the worldwide PV electricity production capacity in the studied scenarios.

Figure 5 –PV electricity production capacity for the four scenarios.

The figure shows that the total installed power in PVs reaches around 9000 GW, meaning more than 30 times the today PV park of around 300 GWp worldwide.

V. CO₂ EMISSIONS IN THE FOUR SCENARIOS

The four scenarios produce a different pattern of CO₂ emissions of the power plants which they shift out. We consider that no PV installations up to 2050 produce a full

CO₂ pattern which we mark as being 1 or 100% (it is in fact about 100% non PV installations from the 50% target considered in the paper, considered as being basic scenario zero). By integrating and mediating the CO₂ emissions in the three scenarios (Scen_x, with x= 1 .. 4), by using the formula:

$$CO_2(Scen_x) = 2 * \sum_{2017}^{2050} (50 - PV_{penetration, year_i}) / (2050 - 2017) \quad (6)$$

where PV_{PENETRATION} is the global (world) share of PV energy production [in %] in each year i (i = 2017 up to 2050), we obtain the following values for the total CO₂ emissions from 2017 till 2050 (Figure 6).

Figure 6 – Total CO₂ emissions [%] in each of the four scenarios.

The values show the emissions in the scenarios 0, 1, 2 and 3, comparing with no action (baseline) from 2017 to 2050 (No PV, black bar). The baseline shows 100% CO₂ emissions for not mounting any PV panel from the share of 50% world energy with PV, thus it was needed the factor 2 in formula (6). Scenarios 1, 2 and 3 save more than 50% of the emissions without any PV deployment. It can be also observed that scenario 2 saves 6.8% emissions compared with scenario 1, while scenario 3 another 5.3% compared with scenario 2. The previous section shows however a big difference in investments for PV panels production between the scenario 3 and the others, making acceptable only scenarios 0, 1 and 2, with higher CO₂ reduction in scenario 2 (around 17% CO₂ savings compared with low effort scenario 0), reduction which can have an important impact on climate change.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The paper aims to analyze the PV panels production capacity which is needed worldwide to reach 50% of the world electrical energy production with PV production. The assessment is made in four different scenarios, for reaching the target in 2050, 2045, 2040 and 2035. The simulation is based

on simplified assumptions, in order to give a first glimpse of the needed capacity.

The results show that the most ambitious target (sooner 50% energy with PVs, in the aggressive year 2035 scenario 3) ask for a much higher production capacity of PV panels, meaning around 600 GWp peak production per year, in order to reach the goal in 2035, meaning nearly 6 times higher than today capacity. In the case of reaching the goal in 2040, 2045 or 2050, the needed peak capacity is between 380 and 420 GWp / year, which shows only a small difference between the scenarios in worldwide panel production capacity of maximum 10%.

Reaching the 50% in PV production in 2040 is better than 5 years later in terms of CO₂ savings, with 6.8% estimated lower emissions. This is an important conclusion showing that the scenario 2 is a good trade-off option for PV capacity development, because it brings more benefits in terms of CO₂ emission reduction compared scenario 1, while asking for a capacity effort only 10% higher. It also shows that the scenario 1 is attractive as well, as it has 10% lower capacity and only 6.8% higher emissions. Both scenarios 1 and 2 ask for a PV panels production capacity of only 4 times today PV production capacity. The accelerated scenario 3 for reaching the 50% goal in 2035 ask for 50% more investments in PV panels production.

The growing factor around 4 needed in scenarios 1 and 2 is in a near range of today production capacity, thus showing that the need for 50% world energy only with PV panels is a feasible target, while keeping shorter time frame for the complete deployment (2040 or 2045), thus better mitigating the climate change concerns as well as the quicker decrease of today high level of pollution.

This situation gives a hope that we can reach or even exceed the targets of the Paris Agreement, if we look on the PV technology and to a credible scaling of the world panel production. Similar situation may be found on wind capacity needs, however this is subject to be treated in future work.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 731155 and No. 727481. This work was also supported by a grant of the Romanian National Authority for Scientific Research and Innovation, CNCS/CCCDI – UEFISCDI, project number PN-III-P3-3.6- H2020-2016-0080-ID 731155, Storage4Grid within PNCDI III.

REFERENCES

- [1] IPCC Special Report on Global Warming of 1.5 °C, 23 october 2017, http://www.ipcc.ch/news_and_events/pr_sr1_expert_review_lam3.shtml, accessed on 23.11.2017
- [2] How high is air pollution in your city and how does it compare to the most polluted cities in the world?,

- <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/0/high-air-pollution-city-does-compare-themost-polluted-cities/>, accessed on 10.11.2017
- [3] China pollution, <http://www.scmp.com/topics/china-pollution>, accessed on 24.11.2017
- [4] Puerto Rico's path to restore power shifts after Whitefish exit, <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-usa-puertorico-power-prepa/puerto-ricos-path-to-restore-power-shifts-after-whitefish-exit-idUSKBN1CZ2T0>, accessed on 10.11.2017
- [5] Cheapest electricity on the planet is Mexican solar power at 1.77¢/kWh – record 1¢/kWh coming in 2019, sooner, <https://electrek.co/2017/11/16/cheapest-electricity-on-the-planet-mexican-solar-power/>, accessed on 24.11.2017
- [6] Rethinking Energy 2017: Accelerating the global energy transformation, IRENA, 2017, http://www.irena.org/documentdownloads/publications/irena_rethinking_energy_2017.pdf, accessed 15.02.2018
- [7] IRENA Renewable energy statistics 2017
- [8] International Energy Agency (2014). "Technology Roadmap: Solar Photovoltaic Energy, 2014 Edition". http://www.iea.org/publications/freepublications/publication/TechnologyRoadmapSolarPhotovoltaicEnergy_2014edition.pdf, IEA. Archived from the original on 7 October 2014. Retrieved 7 October 2014.
- [9] Global Energy System based on 100% Renewable Energy – Power Sector, Lappeenranta University of Technology, Finland, 2017, <http://energywatchgroup.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/Full-Study-100-Renewable-Energy-Worldwide-Power-Sector.pdf>, accessed 10.01.2018
- [10] 100% Clean and Renewable Wind, Water, and Sunlight All-Sector Energy Roadmaps for 139 Countries of the World, <https://web.stanford.edu/group/efmh/jacobson/Articles/I/CountriesWWS.pdf>, accessed on 10.01.2018
- [11] Paris Agreement, <http://bigpicture.unfccc.int/#content-the-paris-agreement>, accessed 10.01.2018
- [12] BP Statistical Review of World Energy June 2017, <https://www.bp.com/content/dam/bp/en/corporate/pdf/energy-economics/statistical-review-2017/bp-statistical-review-of-world-energy-2017-full-report.pdf>
- [13] http://pv.energytrend.com/research/Strong_Chinese_Market_to_Push_Annual_Global_Photovoltaic_Demand_Above_100_GW_for_2017.html
- [14] Chile sets sights on 100% renewables by 2040, <https://www.windpowermonthly.com/article/1454290/chile-sets-sights-100-renewables-2040>, 11 January 2018, accessed 20.01.2018
- [15] Sweden targets 100% renewables by 2040, backs nuclear, <https://renewablesnow.com/news/sweden-targets-100-renewables-by-2040-backs-nuclear-528772/>, accessed 10.01.2018
- [16] California plan for 100% renewable energy by 2045 clears key hurdle, <http://www.latimes.com/politics/essential/la-pol-ca-essential-politics-updates-california-plan-for-100-renewable-1496258464-htmllstory.html>, accessed 10.01.2018
- [17] Can California Achieve 100% Renewable Electricity by 2040? Jerry Brown Thinks So, <https://www.greentechmedia.com/squared/read/california-100-renewables-2040-governor-brown#gs.YbWaRVQ>, accessed 10.01.2018
- [18] San Diego weighs options to reach 100% renewable energy, <https://www.smartcitiesdive.com/news/san-diego-weighs-options-to-reach-100-renewable-energy/511647/>, accessed 10.01.2018